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Abbreviations	
AD	Advertisement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APP	Application
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
B2B	Business To Business
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DCE	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DMP	Data Management Plan
DSS	Decision Support System
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
EP	Exploitation Plan
ES	Exploitation Strategy
EU	European union
Expos	Expositions
E2U	Easy to Use
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPSEO	Greater Paris Seine et Oise Urban Community
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HW/SW	Hardware/Software
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KB	Knowledge Base
KER	Key Expected Results
KM-EP	Knowledge Management for Evidence-Based Practices
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
Med	Medicine

MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MP	Member of Parliament
MS	Microsoft
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NHS	National Health Service
OKP	Open Knowledge Platform
OA	Open-Access
OP	Open Platform
PPP	Power Point Presentation
PP	Power Point
PR	Press Release
RAL	Reichsausschuss für Lieferbedingungen und Gütesicherung
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
R&D	Research and Development
SaaS	Software as a Service
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
Tab	Tabulation
TBD	To Be Determined
Tech	Technology
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UK	United Kingdom
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USD	United States Dollar
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package
WP8L	Work Package 8 Leader

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Executive Summary

The subsequent Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) plan outlines the structure for carrying out appropriate activities throughout the SMILE project's lifespan, as well as the exploitation of the project's results. The deliverable D8.1 provides a comprehensive plan of activities, roadmaps and joint actions to be implemented to maximize the impacts of SMILE solutions, services and methods.

The DCE plan is a deliverable of Work Package 8 "Dissemination, communication and exploitation of results". This DCE plan is designed to ensure the efficient and strategic execution of SMILE's communication activities, dissemination actions and exploitation of results, while reaching a wide range of audiences. Thus, this plan aims to facilitate the general objectives of the SMILE project and its dissemination actions, namely, to boost awareness, promote acceptance, identify synergies, and facilitate the adoption of SMILE solutions, with the aim of encouraging knowledge transfer and providing support for broader adoption at both the EU and global levels.

The D8.1 could undergo slight revisions and extensions based on information received from other work packages and new dissemination opportunities that may emerge throughout the duration of the SMILE project. Therefore, this plan will be periodically updated and followed.

RDIUP, the WP8 leader, with the active collaboration of CIP and FTK and the participation of all partners, will engage in activities such as organising and participating in conferences and workshops. The consortium will also work on the publication and distribution of materials like scientific publications, articles, leaflets, press releases, newsletters, and a website towards accomplishing dissemination of the project's results to a wide range of audiences.

Overall, this deliverable 8.1 comprises 2 interrelated sub-plans:

- Dissemination and Communication (DC) plan that will highlight the activities to be carried out by all partners, showcase the appeal of the SMILE achievements, and share the results with the SMILE community.
- Exploitation plan that will ensure the sustainability of the SMILE post-project and lay the foundation for future market adoption.

1. Introduction to Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan

1.1. Introduction to SMILE project

SMILE is a collaborative project dedicated to harnessing the potential of digital technologies to improve mental health and promote well-being and resilience among young people. In our rapidly evolving society, the younger generation, including children, adolescents, and students, face new digital stressors and post-pandemic challenges. Regrettably, they often find themselves in circumstances where their concerns are not fully understood or acknowledged by adults. This can lead to feelings of discomfort, neglect, and stigmatization, ultimately resulting in negative thoughts and increased social isolation.

On the other side of the spectrum, teachers and parents are overwhelmed and struggle to comprehend the attitudes and emotions of adolescents. This disconnect can lead to frustration and anger, straining their relationships and hindering opportunities for support.

To address these challenges, our multidisciplinary team of experts is exploring the application of AI tools and evidence-based approaches to develop digital solutions and gamified environments that offer support and bridge gaps in self-management and self-care.

SMILE brings together 14 partners from 8 European countries with a great geographical distribution, including 7 EU countries: Germany, Italy, France, Slovenia, Poland, Spain, Romania, and 1 associated country, the United Kingdom.

The consortium includes:

5 Research Centres and Universities: FTK, HWU, UoE, UoM, SWPS

4 SMEs: RDIUP, NION, WIZ, NURO

2 Hospitals: UKH, IRCCS

1 NGO: CIP

1 Mental Health Service Provider: INTRAS

1 Policy Maker: MoM

This consortium possesses the relevant skills and expertise needed for the project, enabling us to develop disruptive technologies and methodologies, based on AI/data analytics, gamification, and Blockchain, to assess the impact of rapid societal changes on psychological distress.

SMILE benefits from a wealth of social and policy expertise through its dedicated partners, as follows:

INTRAS (leading Integr@tención) is a major provider of social and health services.

CIP offers educational and social adhesion services.

IRCCS has strong European networks and focuses on children's wellness and provides social support to young people.

MoM has established a counselling body for the Public Health and Environment Council as a response to social challenges that require changes in societal preferences.

UKH and AUSL-IRCCS will define and lead the progress of different case studies.

7 partners (IRCCS, HWU, INTRAS, SWPS, UKH, CIP and MoM) will carry out the participatory studies and ensure the collection of data. These partners will promote the scaling up of the platform in the countries where they work, supported by other consortium members and under the guidance of SMILE Advisory Board.

Several partners are active in scientific, medical and technological communities, assuring proper transfer of results and recommendations to potential stakeholders, some of whom have already expressed interest.

Figure 1: SMILE Consortium

The SMILE initiative presents a unique opportunity for young people to acquire coping skills, enhance their well-being, and promote resilience. Our gamified scenarios can be accessed both at home and in educational settings, facilitating self-assessment, self-care, and interaction with healthcare professionals. Additionally, experienced individuals will offer peer support.

Through a co-creative process, our apps will empower users with the skills required to manage stress, strengthen family bonds, and increase resilience.

In the context of our research, we delve into the repercussions of stress induced by digitalisation from the user's perspective. Our primary aim is to gain a deeper understanding of its influence on changes in mental well-being, treatment methods, and self-directed management. Clinical practitioners often face challenges in monitoring fluctuations in mental health, which can complicate precise diagnostic processes. Simultaneously, healthcare services are grappling with mounting pressures.

Our mission is centred around the development of inventive methodologies that harness the power of gamification, offering invaluable insights to improve support systems, with a special focus on young individuals.

SMILE is a 42-Months Horizon Project that commenced on 1st May 2023.

1.2. Introduction to Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan

The SMILE consortium is committed to maximizing the impact of its project through significant activities in communication, dissemination, and exploitation. These activities are closely interconnected, targeting effectively specific audiences. SMILE's dissemination activities aim to ensure wide reaching impact and use of project methodological, business, and technological outcomes among different stakeholders' categories (scientists, experts, researchers, policymakers, communities, society at large, etc.). The SMILE dissemination, in synergy with communication and exploitation, is designed to be impact driven. It consists of 3 steps with a view to reach, engage and synergise key target audiences and stakeholders, maximizing the potential outcomes and long-term impacts of the project and the wide scale KERs roll-out.

- Awareness-oriented step: The aim of this phase is to create visibility and raise awareness among all relevant stakeholders during the project's duration.
- Results-oriented step: During this phase, sharing knowledge and findings elaborated within the project will be the main goal. Activities within this phase include the publication of papers in scientific journals, the participation in related conferences, working groups and events, and the active involvement of the stakeholders and end-users in workshops, information days, and the project's demo phases.
- Project after-life step: this phase focuses on identifying the exploitable results of SMILE and working towards their exploitation and utilisation beyond the project's duration. This phase will commence early in the project, but related activities will be intensified during the last year, when the consortium will have a clear view of the scientific and technological results of the project, as well as clear insights from the market and the end-users based on the case studies.

The design of an integrated, impact-based Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan will represent the first milestone governing overall SMILE's DCE activities and will be rolled out in strong synergy with WP2. The DCE strategy aims to inform, share knowledge, and engage with key stakeholders, researchers, end-users and other ongoing EU projects, and the general public through multiple communication materials.

Pilot partners will actively engage with local stakeholders interested in assessing well-being and mental health resilience, as well as educational institutions interested in this field. All partners will participate in the dissemination and communication actions, while industrial partners will contribute to the exploitation of the SMILE outcomes according to their expertise and roles in the project. The table 1. below provides an overview of the key goals and the timeline of the dissemination and exploitation activities.

Table 1: Key goals and Timeline of D&E activities

Timeline	Y1	Y2	Y3 and half	Post-project
Key stakeholders involved in the co-creation	Goal 1: increase awareness and visibility of SMILE project			
	Goal 2: better understand barriers and needs	Goal 3: identify KERs and assess them via	Goal 4: share results and business	Goal 5: Reach TRL 9, exploitation of results and create new business opportunities

		business cases	potential	
Tools	SMILE website, emailing and communication materials			
	Interviews, focus groups and workshops		Face to face meetings, whitepapers	
	Seminars, conferences and events			
Society at large	Goal 6: engage and ensure social implication and adhesion		Goal 8: Continue raising visibility and awareness	
	Goal 7: share public results through networks			
Tools	Website, social media, promotional videos, workshops		Mobile APP, gamification	
			Communication materials	

1.3. Introduction to Dissemination and Communication plan

The primary goal of the DC sub-plan is to efficiently manage and implement strategic dissemination and communication activities, designed to raise awareness, stimulate acceptance, and promote the adoption of SMILE solutions. This document serves as a concise, yet practical toolbox to guide project partners in promoting SMILE Activities.

The objectives of this plan are as follows:

- Provide project partners with practical toolbox and guidelines to identify and capitalize on communication opportunities throughout the project’s lifetime.
- Outline how the project phases, results, and key learnings will be disseminated and promoted to diverse target audiences.
- Engage with the project's target groups through innovative, content-rich communication to effectively reach them.
- Enhance the potential for exploiting SMILE’s results and ensuring their sustainability.

This approach will be characterized by an integrated, impact-focused strategy that engages multiple stakeholders and leverages various communication channels.

The targeted audiences

The table 2. presented below highlights a comprehensive breakdown of the audiences we are targeting and the anticipated impacts that we aim to achieve through our initiatives.

Table 2: Target audiences and expected impacts.

Target Group	Description	Expected impacts
Adolescents	3 groups of ages are considered: young (10 to 14), middle (15 to 18), and late (19 to 24) adolescence. School pupils, university students, patients,	Strengthen their position within the value chain while raising their awareness about mental health. Ensure them access to high-quality care and services.

	migrants.	
Academia	Universities, schools, young researchers, scientists and RTOs	Exchanging expertise and engaging in responsible research linked to psychological distress diagnosis and decision-making processes. Engage at least 10 RTOs
Teachers	Teachers of adolescents	Teach them new and innovative pedagogical methods built upon gamification.
Parents	Parents of adolescents	Inform them about mental health and teach them new skills.
Healthcare Professionals (HP)	Clinicians, hospitals and clinics, psychologists	Enhance their diagnostic and decision-making techniques. Involve at least 1 HP per pilot. Boost their confidence in innovative and disruptive digital technologies.
Businesses	SMEs, Start-ups, Med industries, Health technology and service providers	Speed up the discovery of the R&D findings. Integrate them into innovative systems and services developments. Support 10 SMEs. Generate at least 1 spin-off. Establish at least 5 PPPs.
Policy makers	Public health organizations, MPs, ministries, EC Representatives	Inform them and support them to implement new policies through our OP. Contribute to reducing the costs related to the treatment of psychological distress. Reach out at least 2 policymakers at EU level.
Regulatory bodies	Authorities, governments, public supervisors, agencies	Engage them to early adopt new classifications of mental health digital tools as medical devices. Thus, our consortium will be among the pioneers in offering input on the new regulatory processes.
Investors and insurers	Banks, business angels, health-insurances	Convince them to contribute on jointly funding our post-project development, promote and market our solutions.
Society at large	NGOs, citizens, associations, communities, influencers	Empower individuals and communities to enhance their awareness of their mental health status and promote greater acceptance.

2. Dissemination, and Communication plan

In this section, we introduce the thoughtfully designed Dissemination and Communication Strategy for the SMILE project.

The figure provided below illustrates a visualization of the four key phases and associated activities that propel our dissemination and communication endeavours, demonstrating the project's journey towards achieving its WP8 goals.

Figure 2: The key phases and activities of WP8

Moreover, to deliver an even more comprehensive overview of our strategy's implementation, we have designed a captivating visual roadmap. This roadmap features active participation from our project partners, outlining their designated responsibilities and deliverables. Each leading partner's unique role is depicted within the roadmap, contributing to the collective effort as we navigate the diverse landscape of SMILE's Dissemination, Communication, Engagement and Exploitation initiatives.

Figure 3: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Roadmap

2.1. Detailed dissemination and communication plan

The strategy focuses on establishing and executing a realistic and practical dissemination and communication plan in line with the project's evolution. It involves selecting suitable tools, channels, and activities to engage with the target audiences in a defined timeline.

2.1.1. Dissemination and communication guidelines

In line with our commitment to transparency and accountability, the SMILE project adheres to specific guidelines that govern its communication, ensuring that our work is conducted in a responsible and ethical manner. The communication guidelines are the bone structure of the dissemination and communication activities. They were proposed by the WP8 leader, RDIUP, and agreed upon by all project partners during an online workshop in June 2023.

To build a robust and distinctive identity for SMILE, we have not only designed visual elements for the project identity, including the logo and the templates, but we also created a set of rules

and guidelines to help project partners in efficiently and effectively promoting SMILE's branding image.

Main guidelines:

Below we outline the main guidelines that not only reflect our acknowledgment of the support received from the EU's Horizon Europe Programme but also emphasize our independence in expressing our findings:

- **Disclaimer:** This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101080923.

- **Legal notice:** Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use, which might be made, of the following information. The views expressed in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission.

- **Scientific Acknowledgment:** This work has been carried out in the framework of European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101080923. (SMILE: Supporting Mental Health in Young People: Integrated Methodology for clinical decisions and evidence-based interventions).

Use the disclaimer in all project's documents, both internal and external, to reference the project's funding source. Use the legal notice in all documents delivered by the Consortium to specify responsibilities and information usage. Incorporate the scientific acknowledgment in all produced documents to recognise the association of the work with the EU's Horizon Europe Programme.

The main guidelines are available for [download](#) for all project partners in an excel sheet provided by RDIUP and uploaded in FTK NextCloud. In the same link, RDIUP provided the official translations of the disclaimer and legal notice in all 24 official languages of the European Union.

General guidelines:

In our pursuit of consistency and professionalism, our general guidelines adhere not only to certain standards when it comes to document formatting and language use, but also when it comes to collaboration and documentation processes. To ensure an inclusive communication, especially when engaging with the public and younger audiences, we have established the following general guidelines:

- **Font and formatting:**
 - Use Arial as the font for documents generated with MS Office and for web applications.
 - Maintain a font size and style that ensures readability, with a particular emphasis on using a larger font size for younger audiences. Left alignment is highly recommended, as it can improve readability for individuals with dyslexia.
 - Incorporate sufficient spacing of 6pt between paragraphs to enhance document clarity.

- Colour Scheme
 - Employ the prescribed colour scheme based on RAL and HEX codes for all SMILE’s communication materials and presentations, both internal and external. The recommended RAL and HEX colour codes are as follows:

Table 3: SMILE RAL Colour Codes

Items	SMILE – RAL and HEX Colour Codes
Background	Light shade of Orange #fdf4ee
Text	Black #000000, White #ffffff, Gray#222023 and Green #00bf63
Figures	Mainly Green #00bf63 and Magenta #cb6ce6
Full Logo	RAL 1002RAL 1003RAL 1016 RAL 1017 RAL 1018 RAL 1023RAL 1026 RAL 1034RAL 2003RAL 2012 RAL 3012 RAL 3014 RAL 3017 RAL 3018 RAL 3022 RAL 4003RAL 4006 RAL 4008 RAL 4010RAL 5002 RAL 5005RAL 5012RAL 5014 RAL 5015 RAL 5017 RAL 5018 RAL 5026RAL 6011 RAL 6016RAL 6018 RAL 6024 RAL 6026 RAL 6027 RAL 6029 RAL 6037 RAL 6038RAL 9003RAL 9016
Icon S:	RAL 1016 RAL 4003RAL 4006 RAL 4008 RAL 5002 RAL 5014RAL 6011 RAL 6016RAL 6018 RAL 6024 RAL 6026RAL 9003RAL 9016

- Language use:
 - Employ UK English as the standard language for all written communication.
- Content accessibility:
 - Prioritize the use of easy-to-understand (E2U) language to make content more accessible, especially when targeting younger audiences.
 - Emphasise the prevalence of images over textual information to engage and capture the attention of a diverse audience.
 - Ensure that all images and pictures used in communication materials are properly licensed to avoid copyright infringement.
- Image sources:
 - Always provide clear and accessible sources for images and pictures used in communication materials while complying with the license conditions of use (preferably premium). This enhances transparency and credibility.

These inclusive communication guidelines are designed to make our content more accessible and engaging for a wide range of audiences. In addition to these guidelines, we continue to uphold the following general guidelines for collaboration:

- Notify RDIUP, FTK, and CIP about DC activities.

- Continuously update the DC tool, which was jointly created by RDIUP and CIP, to streamline our documentation processes.

By integrating these general inclusive communication rules with our existing practices, we aim to provide content that is not only informative, but also accessible and engaging to all our stakeholders.

Website and social media guidelines

The SMILE's [website](#) and social media channels are serving as essential touchpoints with our audience. To make the most of these platforms, we have established guidelines to direct our online interactions:

- Collect photos and videos for all SMILE activities and share them with FTK and RDIUP for use on the website and on social media.
- Contribute actively to the news section of the website, with at least one news item per month per partner.
- Inform the WP8 Leader about every event you organize or participate in, providing a link to the event.
- Inform the WP8 Leader about news articles and posts (e.g., newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) for more online visibility.
- Register for all SMILE Medias (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, TikTok and YouTube) Promote and share SMILE Media within your network of contacts.
- Signal to RDIUP relevant accounts and sister projects to be followed on social media.
- If you create a short video, enhance it with the project identity, by including the name of the project, the logo, the EU emblem and the disclaimer.

Project partners are expected to follow these guidelines consistently, ensuring a unified and coherent use of visual elements in all project-related communication materials, both online and offline.

Project Identity guidelines

In line with the communication guidelines, a project identity has been set up at the project's outset, which includes SMILE's logo and templates for project deliverables, general project documents and project PowerPoint presentations. The project identity will support our dissemination activities and ensure a consistent communication of the project's idea, objectives and results.

Logo

The project logo is a crucial graphic element that must be used consistently and suitably. In this regard, 2 versions of transparent SMILE logo have been designed. They are available for [download](#) for all project partners.

Figure 4: SMILE logos

2.2. Document templates

A [PP template](#) was designed displaying the partners logos on its front page. This template is used for all presentations and meetings, whether they are targeting internal or external audiences.

Figure 5: PPP template example – 1st and last slide

Also, we created [word templates](#) to ensure the coherence of the visuals including SMILE font styles and colours. These templates are defined to be used as a base for all documents produced within the project.

The deliverable template as well as the peer review evaluation form template are shown in Figures 6 and 7.

On the “Home” tab of the word templates, font styles were predefined for both body text and headings. They appear automatically. For the colours, the documents have been assigned a SMILE colour palette to help maintain the visual identity of the project.

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DX.X Report on Communication engagement, dissemination, and exploitation plan

Project Number: 101080923
Project Acronym: SMILE

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Figure 6: Deliverable template – 1st and last pages

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Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?				
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SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

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<input type="checkbox"/> Document not accepted, changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/> Document not accepted, it must be reviewed again after changes are implemented.

Document name:	D X.X Peer Review Evaluation Form	Page:	3 of 3
Dissemination:	DD		

Figure 7: Peer review evaluation form template

2.3. Communication materials

The communication materials, including leaflets, flyers, posters, roll-ups, and factsheet, have been designed, created, translated into several languages (e.g. English, Dutch, Slovene, French, and Greek) and distributed within the consortium. These materials are now ready for wider dissemination. The SMILE consortium plans to distribute them through various European and global information channels and online media platforms such as Alpha Galileo, Physorg, Cordis Wire, youris.com, leveraging their extensive reach and audience.

- [Flyer](#)
- [Leaflet](#)
- [Factsheet](#)
- [Roll-up](#)
- [Simplified Roll-up](#)

Figure 8: Flyer

Figure 9: Roll-up – detailed and simplified version

Figure 10: The SMILE Leaflet

Figure 11: Factsheet

2.4. Project website

The project's web portal to be developed initially by M6 (D8.2), stands as the primary gateway to access a wealth of information pertaining to SMILE's activities, deliverables, news and events. This website will display essential project details, partner profiles, results, event updates, and direct links to partner institutions. This website will be available at: <https://www.horizonmile.eu/>.

Among its key functions, the project website will serve as a central hub for making all public deliverables readily accessible through downloadable links. More than a static information repository, this website will actively facilitate communication and information dissemination. It will act as the primary conduit for sharing project updates with a broad and diverse audience.

The website is designed with a dynamic interface, featuring an attractive design and user-friendly navigation. It will incorporate multimedia elements and informative sections to introduce users to the SMILE partnership, elucidating its underlying concept, vision, objectives, and ongoing activities.

As the project evolves, the web portal will be continuously updated with publishable deliverables, promotional materials and event details. The partners will actively contribute to the news section of the website by 5 news items per partner per year, ensuring the site remains current and engaging.

Every effort will be made to keep the project website active for several years beyond the project's lifespan.

SMILE website will participate in <https://webawards.eurid.eu/> to increase visibility.

Figure 12: Launching of SMILE's website by the end of October 2023

2.5. Project social media

The communication channels will focus on strengthening the project's presence at both the European and global levels. Engaging in social media initiatives is recognized as a powerful tool to amplify the project's influence and disseminate information widely.

SMILE's social media platforms include:

- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Twitter](#)
- [Facebook](#)
- [TikTok](#)
- [YouTube](#)

Figure 13: LinkedIn profile

Figure 14: Twitter profile

Figure 15: Facebook profile

Figure 16: TikTok profile

Figure 17: YouTube profile

These platforms will serve as hubs for discussions, comments, input, and the exploration of research and policy topics with a diverse range of stakeholders across various levels. The Facebook and Twitter accounts will be used to inform the broader community about both technical and non-technical aspects. Tweets will include relevant hashtags such as #mental_health, #HorizonEurope, and #innovation, to increase their visibility. When posting Tweets that need to direct users to specific pages on the website, it's advisable to use shortened URL links.

The YouTube and TikTok profiles will be used to disseminate all promotional videos on the web. The LinkedIn presence will serve as a professional platform for discussions, interactions, information gathering and the communication of project outputs to experts, including researchers, industries, SMEs, NGOs, local authorities, and more. Additionally, it offers the opportunity to join and actively participate in significant groups related to the project's fields.

Each partner is expected to become a member or follower of the project's social media profiles and actively engage with them. Active participation involves commenting on project-related posts and sharing publishable content within their personal networks.

The management of social media is overseen by the WP8 leader, RDIUP. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to regularly share posts and updates about SMILE through their respective organizational social media channels (KPIs are provided in subsection 4.3). Direct links to SMILE's social media profiles will be accessible on the website.

3. Dissemination and Communication planned activities

The dissemination and communication of SMILE's innovative concepts, research outcomes and results take shape through a wide array of methods and initiatives. Our approach extends beyond reaching our target audience. It focuses on engaging them in a meaningful and collaborative manner. Through these diverse activities, we strive to connect with stakeholders, share valuable insights, and create opportunities for dialogue and collaboration. Each of these methods serves a unique purpose in our overall communication strategy, contributing to the ultimate success of our project. Our commitment to effective communication and dissemination is evident in the variety of activities we employ.

3.1. Newsletters

The project will produce a newsletter every six months. These newsletters will provide up to date information on the project's progress, achievements, upcoming tasks, and events, in addition to news from similar initiatives and relevant scientific fields.

The newsletters will be prepared by RDIUP, with input from relevant partners regarding the content. The specifics of the content will be determined and agreed upon within the consortium.

A mailing-list will be established to facilitate mass mailing, which will be compiled from contact lists obtained through website registrations, enabling visitors to subscribe to the newsletter in accordance with GDPR rules, and from contact lists gathered during the events. This mailing list will be continuously updated throughout the project.

The newsletters will also be accessible on the project website. Each partner will translate the newsletter into their local language and utilize it.

3.2. Journalistic articles and Interviews

Press releases are effective for capturing journalists' attention by highlighting newsworthy developments and significant project milestones. To enhance outreach, we are constructing a database of relevant newspaper editors from regional, national, and EU press. This database will facilitate precise targeting of press releases and effective engagement with media partners.

Our inaugural press release marked the official launch of the SMILE project. To maintain regular communication and engagement, a designated partner will oversee a Press Release (PR) every 3 months (Independent.co.uk¹ done by HWU).

To ensure wide visibility, PRs will be available on the project website and widely distributed to external media channels to publicize significant project updates and developments.

¹ <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/social-media-mental-health-effects-young-people-study-b2347534.html>

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Project Acronym: SMILE

For local relevance, each PR will undergo translation and adaptation for specific local contexts. Subsequently, each partner will share these tailored PRs with their respective local media and press offices.

Radio interviews will serve as a powerful medium to convey project updates, news, project results, success stories, and valuable lessons learned. Our partner HWU has engaged with BBC Radio Scotland on their 'Good Morning Scotland' program to showcase the SMILE project and explore how gamification and digital solutions can revolutionize youth mental health support.

Furthermore, our partners are in the process of arranging interviews on multiple radio stations. This strategic approach aims to enhance the visibility and recognition of SMILE, thereby further engaging stakeholders and the public.

3.3. Videos

The consortium has created an engaging animated promotional video on YouTube to provide a general presentation and introduction to the project in English. Recognizing the importance of reaching diverse audiences, this video has also been translated into Spanish, Slovenian, Greek, German, Polish and Italian.

These captivating videos serve as a dynamic tool to convey the project's goals and mission. They will be featured on the project website and relayed through the YouTube platform and social medial accounts, ensuring easy access for all target audiences.

Figure 18: Promotional SMILE videos

To maximize visibility and impact, all partners are committed to promoting these videos through their respective communication channels.

3.4. Scientific publications

The consortium will publish at least 8 scientific publications and/or articles.

As part of the Extended Open Research Data Pilot, we commit to an Open Access approach for scientific publications, ensuring free, online access to peer-reviewed scientific publications

related to our project results, following both green and gold models as defined in article 29.2 of the GA.

These publications will also be available on the project website.

The consortium drafts an indicative list of relevant scientific mental health and AI-related journals and circulates it among partners.

Table 4: List of relevant scientific project-related journals

List of relevant scientific project-related journals	
-Journal of Clinical Epidemiology	-JMIR (Journal of Medical Internet Research)
-eLIFE Sciences	-International Journal of Medical Informatics
-Plos Medicine	-New Media and Society
-Plos Digital Health	-Journal of Psychosomatic Research
-The American Journal of Psychiatry	-Neuroscience & Biobehavioural Reviews
-JMIR Mental Health	-The Child & Adolescent Mental Health (CAMH)
-International Journal of Depression and Anxiety	-The international Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education (IJAIED)
-Digital health Journal	-Children and Youth Services Review
-The Lancet Digital Health	-Journal of Paediatric Psychology
-Computers and Education	-Journal of Cognitive Enhancement
-Human-Computer Interaction	-Simulation & Gaming
-Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research (JAIR)	-AI & Society
-International Journal of Computer Games Technology	-Computers in Human Behaviour
-International Journal of Serious Games	-Entertainment Computing

Each partner is responsible for identifying and pursuing publishing opportunities.

The consortium will design a white paper guideline to strengthen our presence within the healthcare sector by documenting the best practices, suggesting policy instructions, and facilitating communication with stakeholders to showcase our partners' high-level expertise.

3.5. Conferences

The SMILE consortium will host one main public event at the end of the project, known as the final event. This conference will be open to anyone interested in attending. To ensure a broad audience presence, invitations will be sent to key stakeholders in the field.

The aim of the conference is to disseminate the acquired knowledge and showcase the final achievements to all identified stakeholder groups, including academic and research scientists, industry professionals, government officials, policy makers, and anyone interested. The objective is to foster policy influence and promote the utilisation of project results in industry, research and society.

The primary goals of the final conference are:

- To enable external stakeholders, who are not directly engaged in the project, to be briefed on key results reached at significant project milestones and foster an interactive discussion with them.
- To assess the feasibility of implementing the proposed solutions.

A Press Release will be diffused prior to the event “Save The Date”. The program, presentations, or articles of SMILE’s final conference will be available on the project website.

In addition to the final conference, SMILE consortium will leverage their involvement in external conferences as an extra opportunity to gain access to new networking channels, forge collaborations with end-users, sponsors and exhibitors and any other initiatives sharing similar objectives.

The partners will attend and contribute to relevant conferences that align with the domain of interest of the project. RDIUP and CIP drafts an indicative list of target conferences and circulates it among partners.

Table 5: Indicative list of relevant project-related external conferences

Name of conferences	Place	Date
Mental Health & Well-Being Global Summit	Online	October 17-23, 2023
Gamification Europe 2023	Utrecht, Netherlands	October 26-27, 2023
Virtual Reality Mental Health Conference	Groningen, Netherlands	November 9-10, 2023
World Congress on Primary Healthcare and Medicare Summit	Dubai, United Arab Emirates	November 13-14, 2023
European Health Summit	Brussels, Belgium	December 7, 2023
European Epidemiology and Public Health Congress	Roma, Italy	December 14-15, 2023
AIMday Health tech	Edinburgh, UK	January 30, 2024

Deutscher Kongress für Psychosomatische Medizin und Psychotherapie (DKPM)	Berlin, Germany	March 13-15, 2024
6th World Mental Health Congress	Online	April 15-16, 2024
6th World Congress on Mental Health	Barcelona, Spain	May 9-10, 2024
The 13th Swedish Congress on Internet Interventions (SweSRII)	Stockholm, Sweden	May 20-21, 2024
The 12th International Society for Research on Internet Interventions (ISRII) Scientific Meeting	Limerick, Ireland	June 2-5, 2024
The International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications & Innovations	Corfu, Greece Hybrid	June 27-30, 2024
The 10th International Conference on Virtual Reality (ICVR)	Bournemouth, United Kingdom	July 20-22, 2024
12th International Conference on Serious Games and Applications for Health	Funchal, Portugal	August 7-9, 2024
International Conference on Healthcare Service Management (ICHSM)	Istanbul, Turkey	September 6-8, 2024
European Health Summit	Brussels, Belgium	2024 (exact date: TBD)
The 14th Swedish Congress on Internet Interventions (SweSRII)	To be Determined	2025 (exact date: TBD)
The 12th International Society for Research on Internet Interventions (ISRII) Scientific Meeting	To be Determined	2025 (exact date: TBD)
European Health Summit	Brussels, Belgium	2025 (exact date: TBD)
European Health Summit	Brussels, Belgium	2026 (exact date: TBD)

To meet the specifications of T8.2 as outlined in the proposal, CIP recommends the SMILE consortium's attendance at the European Health Summit at Egmond Palace in Brussels. The upcoming summit is scheduled for December 7, 2023. This event takes place annually, allowing the SMILE consortium the opportunity to participate on a yearly basis throughout the project's duration. For further details, please consult the [European Health Summit website](#).

3.6. Events, Expos and Seminars

In our pursuit of knowledge exchange and networking, the SMILE consortium actively participates in a wide array of events, including expos, seminars and any other pertinent gatherings.

The following table provides a compilation of our selected events and is made accessible to all consortium partners.

Table 6: Indicative list of relevant project-related events (Expos, seminars)

Name	Place	Date
Tim Althoff: How Human-AI Collaboration Will Improve Mental Health	Online	December 5, 2023
Warsaw Medical Expo	Warsaw, Poland	December 6-8, 2023
Children's Mental Health Week	United Kingdom Virtual	February 5-11, 2024
4YFN Digital Health Event	Barcelona, Spain	February 26-29, 2024
Web Summit Rio	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	April 15-18, 2024
Gitex Africa 2024	Marrakech, Morocco	May 8-10, 2024
Health Expo	Paris, France	May 21-23, 2024
Viva Technology	Paris, France	May 22-25, 2024
Sifted Summit	London, UK	October 2-3, 2024
World Mental Health Day 2024	Virtual (World Health Organization)	October 10, 2024
World Mental Health Day 2025	Virtual (World Health Organization)	October 10, 2025
World Mental Health Day 2026	Virtual (World Health Organization)	October 10, 2026
Gitex Global 2024	Dubai, UAE	To be determined
Gitex Global 2025	To be Determined	To be Determined

CIP will generate Internal Circulars on a quarterly basis, containing information on events, conferences and potential activities relevant to the SMILE consortium's objectives and interests. All partners are encouraged to inform the T8.2 leader, CIP, on any identified national or international upcoming opportunities, to ensure their inclusion in the circular. Here is the timeline created by CIP:

Figure 19: Timeline for the distribution of internal circulars

The T8.2 leader, CIP, has designed a tool, “identification of conferences, events and initiatives”, with the purpose of gathering information from partners regarding potential opportunities at local, national and international levels. This tool is used by both CIP and RDIUP to streamline their collaborative efforts in collecting and internally disseminating information promptly.

Demo-site showcases:

The consortium planned to organize a series of demo-site showcases in collaboration with municipalities and local governments. These showcases are designed as dynamic and interactive platforms where participants will have the opportunity to explore and firsthand experience the innovative solutions and methodologies developed within the SMILE project. These events aim to not only inform but actively engage and educate our target audience, ensuring that they play a pivotal role in shaping the future of mental health support for young individuals. The primary goal is to create a vibrant and interactive environment where local communities can unite, learn, share, and contribute to the cause embraced by SMILE.

Training sessions:

SMILE’s consortium recognises the importance of knowledge sharing and training among our consortium members. To this end, our partners have planned an extensive and multidisciplinary training program which incorporates a hybrid approach, combining virtual and in-person training sessions. This program will span bi-weekly demonstrations and training packages, totalling more than 6 enlightening sessions. The primary objective of this initiative is to equip participants with a wide array of skills and in-depth knowledge, thereby enhancing their understanding of project components and ensuring the successful implementation of our project, ultimately maximizing its impact.

To organise and coordinate these sessions effectively, we have established bi-weekly technical meetings. As of the most recent updates:

- FTK has successfully conducted a training session for SAPL and has confirmed their 2nd training session, which will showcase the demo KM-EP.
- RDIUP and WIZ have provided details about their respective demos, with plans for training sessions in upcoming bi-weekly workshops.
- No confirmation received from NION, NURO, and UoM regarding their training packages.

All partners are encouraged to confirm their demo presentations and training packages as soon as possible.

For a summarised view, refer to the table below offering a clear overview of the training packages and demo presentations status for each partner within the consortium.

Table 7: Training packages -Partner responsible and status

Partners	Demo presentation and training package	Status
FTK	SAPL Python	Completed September 15, 2023
FTK	Knowledge management-Ecosystem Portal (KM-EP) demo	Upcoming November 15, 2023 (To be Confirmed)
RDIUP	Quiz based recommender system	Upcoming November 29, 2023 (To Be Confirmed)
WIZ	Medical data management for hospital	Upcoming December 13, 2023 (To Be Confirmed)
NION	Cloud based platform (To Be Defined)	Awaiting confirmation 2024 (To Be Determined)
NURO	Existing gamification (To Be Defined)	Awaiting confirmation 2024 (To Be Determined)
UoM	Interactive Chatbot (To Be Defined)	Awaiting confirmation 2024 (To Be Determined)

Workshops:

The Consortium has planned an extensive schedule of workshops to ensure comprehensive exploration of various facets of the SMILE project. These workshops are strategically designed to cater to the needs of different stakeholders and cover a wide range of topics. Here's a detailed description of these workshops:

Dedicated Workshops with Potential End-Users and Experts: The Consortium will host 4 specialized workshops, specifically tailored to engage with potential end-users and experts. These workshops will serve as platforms for valuable input, feedback, and collaboration.

Pilot-Specific Workshops: To ensure the success of each pilot, at least one dedicated workshop per pilot will be organized. These workshops will focus on addressing the unique requirements and challenges of each pilot, fostering an environment for productive discussions and collaborative problem-solving.

Technical Workshops: A series of 4 technical workshops will be conducted, each dedicated to a specific technical aspect of the project. These workshops will cover essential topics such as gamification, Knowledge Management for Evidence-Based Practices (KM-EP), Mobile App development, and Decision Support Systems (DSS).

Integration Workshops: In addition to the pilot-specific and technical workshops, integration workshops will be held to bring together all modules of the project. These workshops are vital for ensuring seamless collaboration and effective integration of various components, ultimately contributing to the success of the SMILE project.

With this comprehensive workshop schedule, the Consortium aims to provide a well-rounded learning and collaboration experience, ensuring the project's objectives are met effectively.

Figure 20: Initial Workshops roadmap

Webinars

The consortium is committed to fostering knowledge sharing and community engagement through a series of enlightening webinars. We have scheduled 3 public webinars annually, each addressing vital aspects of the SMILE project. These webinars serve as a platform to not only disseminate valuable insights and project updates but mainly to encourage active participation and interaction with interested stakeholders and audiences.

3.7. Joint actions

The Consortium will actively engage in 5 joint actions, including those facilitated through Horizon Result Booster initiatives and collaborative workshops. By engaging in these shared endeavours, we aim to leverage collective expertise, foster innovative collaborations, and drive the project's success. These joint actions will serve as dynamic platforms for mutual learning, idea exchange, and the advancement of mental health support for young individuals.

At this stage, a first virtual meeting has been scheduled between RDIUP and CIP, to define the upcoming steps for our joint actions. Here is the roadmap we have established:

- RDIUP: Leveraging RDIUP's experience in stakeholder engagement, joint actions, and clustering from various EU-funded projects, RDIUP shared preparatory and process-oriented documents. These documents serve as valuable resources, offering inspiration, ideas, and examples for the SMILE consortium. RDIUP will establish contacts with sister projects.
- CIP: Takes the lead in drafting the initial ideas and sub-task plans for this joint activity. Following CIP's draft, RDIUP will review it and provide essential feedback.
- Subsequently, CIP and RDIUP will prepare essential materials to support this activity, including Excel recording tools, stakeholder identification surveys, detailed plans, and clear deadlines, for the successful execution of our joint actions.

Among the activities, the consortium will engage in networking activities with sister projects. The aim of this activity is to gain knowledge, create networks, explore cooperation activities, identify non-tech obstacles, and learn about possible solutions to overcome these barriers.

Figure 21: Timeline for the development of a group of sister projects and the implementation of the group's joint activities

The timeline above present SMILE's joint actions with sister projects throughout the project's duration. At this stage, we already contacted (excluding n°101080238) the sister projects that we have identified and listed below:

Table 8: SMILE sister projects

Project ID	Title	Acronym
101081020	A complex systems approach towards RESilient and CONNECTED vulnerable European communities in times of change	RECONNECTED
101080665	Augmented Social Play (ASP): smartphone-enabled group psychotherapeutic interventions that boost adolescent mental health by supporting real-world connection	ASP-belong

	and sense of belonging	
101080238	Boosting Societal Adaptation and Mental Health in a Rapidly Digitalizing, Post-Pandemic Europe	Bootstrap
101080651	Protecting mental health in times of change	MENTBEST
101080323	Addressing Mental Health Vulnerabilities from Adolescence to Older Age: Innovating Prevention Science for Times of Change	ADVANCE
101080934	E-Intervention Enhancing Mental Health in Adolescents	IMPROVA

Furthermore, SMILE will mobilise its networks with key stakeholders and associations to distribute news and content through their channels and possibly participate in major events organized under their sponsorship. SMILE has already garnered interest from more than 15 hospitals, schools, universities, and municipalities across Europe, showcasing the appeals of the tools provided by the consortium.

Through proactive networking and discussions with European and national associations and platforms, SMILE aims to broaden its reach. Also, clustering and cross-fertilization activities will be carried out to exploit synergies for the benefit of the project. Among these clusters and networks, SMILE partners are involved in: European Network of Aging, National and International Rotary Clubs, Italian Higher Institute of Health, British Psychological Society, DGMS (German Society for Medical Sociology), Digital Innovation Hub, WHO, NHS and GPSEO.

These partnerships will further strengthen SMILE's ability to advance mental health support for young individuals.

The joint actions also include planning actions and activities aimed at establishing links with local communities, stakeholders and policymakers. The SMILE consortium aims to develop a stakeholder network through its communication and dissemination activities such as events and conference participation and organization. For this reason, a Stakeholder Identification Dataset has been created by CIP, inviting all consortium members to register local, national, European and International stakeholders alongside their prospective interest, involvement and impact in SMILE activities. This will allow the development of the SMILE stakeholder network, inviting their contribution in various activities at both national and international level.

Here is the timeline created by CIP:

Figure 22: Timeline for establishing links with local communities, stakeholders and policymakers.

3.8. Development of feedback and recommendations for policy makers

By establishing a collaborative framework involving SMILE's sister projects and identifying actions that can mutually benefit the collective effort, the T8.2 leader will formulate recommendations for policymakers.

SMILE's sister projects share thematic areas that offer valuable insights for shaping policy decisions. Potential collaborative actions between these projects may include the organization of Policy-making labs, featuring the participation of expert project panelists and key stakeholders, including policymakers, healthcare professionals, and educators.

SMILE's primary focus is to devise recommendations for policymakers in the realm of e-mental health solutions for young individuals, exploring their potential integration in educational environments, and investigating the application of gamification and AI in mental health. The goal of all collaborative initiatives involving policymakers is to produce a concise Policy Recommendations document, which will be disseminated at events, conferences, and public awareness campaigns.

Alongside external network working groups, these policy recommendations and feedback from policymakers will be integrated into the Municipality of Maribor's internal processes. For instance, after the completion of living labs, insights into policy recommendations can be drafted. Consequently, a Strategy for Policy Elaborations will be formulated during the project's 2nd year.

Sub-activity 4 is anticipated to commence toward the conclusion of the project's 3rd year, following the development of the gamified system. This timing is essential to ensure the availability of a preliminary prototype of the gamified environment and, ideally, initial validation results from clinical trials at pilot sites. As this activity is closely tied to the outcomes and progression of sub-activity 3, additional information regarding the process and recommendations for actions will be provided in the forthcoming revised version of this plan.

Figure 23: Timeline for the development of policy recommendations and actions

4. Overview of dissemination activities, responsible partners and expected impacts

In this section we'll present a table for a comprehensive overview of the various dissemination activities that will be undertaken, including the key partners responsible for their execution and elucidating the expected impacts these activities will generate.

Table 9: Overview of dissemination activities, responsible partners and expected impacts.

Activities	Responsible	Expected impacts and indicators
Journals	All scientific partners	Increase the scientific productions of the consortium. Increase the impact factors and ranking of researchers. N° of Gold Open Access with high Impact Factor or in self-archiving green access with repositories listed in Zenodo. At least 8 articles and/or publications.
Conferences	All academic and scientific partners	Learn from scientific sessions and workshops. Ensure effective Transfer technologies and disseminate the RDI activities of SMILE. Attend 1 or more conferences per partner during the project.
Events / seminars	All scientific and technical partners	Gain access to new networking channels. Establish novel cooperation with end-users and meet with sponsors and exhibitors. Present our solutions in 6 events per year.
Events to be organised by SMILE		
Guidelines	HWU	Reinforce the influence and spread of the consortium in the healthcare sectors. Report the best practices, the suggested instructions policies and the recommendations in a white paper published in an open repository (e.g., Open Research Europe) and through SMILE platforms.
Webinars	WP Leaders	Engage new stakeholders and open discussion to collect feedback. Organise 3 public webinars per year.
Co-creation and technical Workshops	All partners and co-creators	Showcase our findings and implicate stakeholders in the SMILE ecosystem and concepts, co-design and share findings and results. A roadmap of: At least one co-creation workshop per pilot, 4 technical workshops (gamification, KM-EP, Mobile APP, DSS), and 2 workshops for all modules integration with an average of 20 participants (organisations) each.
Virtual and physical	FTK, NURO, AUSL-IRCCS,	Elaborate scientific and technological contents and train practitioners, technical staff, students and young researchers.

trainings	HWU	Four sessions of 3 days.
Collaboration and SMILE community	All	Establish collaborative partnerships and cross-country research. Exchange evidence-based practices and findings. 5 relevant joint actions (e.g., via Booster Horizon Result Booster and workshops) with existing projects and platforms (e.g., extend the KB, policy recommendations, replication, seminar, challenge). Involve at least 20 multidisciplinary members in the SMILE community.
Final Event	FTK and all stakeholders	Showcase the outcomes of the project, carry out demonstrations and create strong collaborations. At least 100 participants and a high satisfaction index.

4.1. The key information and message to be disseminated.

The dissemination process will focus on conveying crucial information and key messages, which encompass various aspects of the project. This will include, but is not limited to:

- Exploitable results from previous WPs: The project's achievements and findings from preceding Work Packages will be presented in a concise and actionable manner. These outcomes form the foundation for further progress within the SMILE project.

- Comprehensive SMILE overview: To ensure a well-rounded understanding of the project, the dissemination will cover SMILE's key facts, core objectives, and expected outcomes. This includes a clear and accessible explanation, avoiding technical jargon reaching a broad audience.

- Highlighting SMILE events: Various project events, including workshops, training sessions, and conferences, will be showcased. This will provide opportunities for partners and stakeholders to engage with the project's activities.

- Showcasing SMILE achievements and results: The dissemination process will emphasize the project's accomplishments and results. These may include the development of innovative tools, the successful implementation of pilot activities, and key findings derived from research. These achievements are essential in advancing the project's goals and impact.

4.2. Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination and communication activities

The success of our dissemination and communication activities is paramount in achieving our project's objectives. To ensure that our efforts are impactful and aligned with our goals, we have implemented a robust monitoring and evaluation tool.

This process involves systematically collecting data from our ongoing D&C activities. We have created a dedicated spreadsheet for this purpose, making it readily accessible online for our partners, and consistently updating it.

Each partner is responsible for updating their dedicated sheet, that is composed of the following tabs (Figure 24), which seamlessly syncs with the global monitoring sheet (Figure 25), the dashboard (Figure 26), the number of followers (Figure 27), and the audience reached (Figure 28). This collaborative system ensures that we have real-time insights into the impact of our D&C activities.

Social media activities and communication						
Social media*	Type of activities*	Description	Include link (if available)	Reporting Period*	Type of audience*	Estimation of reached people*
<i>[Please use 1 row per publication]</i>	<i>[Type of social media publication]</i>	<i>[Brief description of the activity]</i>	<i>[url if available]</i>	<i>[RP1 or RP2 or RP3]</i>	<i>Select key target audience</i>	<i>Rough estimation</i>

Website activities and communication						
Type of Web ACTIVITIES*	Link*	Reporting Period*	Type of audience*	Estimation of reached people*	Notes	
<i>[Please use 1 row per publication]</i>	<i>Link of the Web publication</i>	<i>[RP1 or RP2 or RP3]</i>	<i>Select key target audience</i>	<i>Rough estimation</i>	<i>details</i>	

Scientific publications												
Status of the article/publication*	Author/s*	Title	Publication title*	Month/Year	short description	DOI (if available)*	Other link (if available)	Open access (y/n)*	If yes, Open Access repository link if different than indicated on columns G and H	Reporting Period*	Type of audience*	Estimation of reached people*
<i>[Scientific, professional, policy other (please specify)]</i>	<i>[surname, name]</i>	<i>[Title of the article]</i>	<i>[Title of the journal]</i>	<i>[year of publication]</i>	<i>[numbering of the journal - if applicable]</i>	<i>[url if available]</i>	<i>[other link if DOI is not available]</i>	<i>[Answer YES if the publication indicated in column D is an open access journal]</i>	<i>[Only required if there is not a DOI or other link accessing the complete text]</i>	<i>[RP1 or RP2 or RP3]</i>	<i>Select key target audience</i>	<i>Rough estimation</i>

Figure 24: Monitoring tool - Tabs

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No 101080923.		Scientific publications	Events and conference activities	Social activities	Website activities	Total	Post	Video	Organization of Conference	Co-creation Workshops	Technical Workshops	Webinars	Virtual/Physical Trainings	Participation in a Conference	Participation in a Workshop	Summer school	Seminars	Fairs	Expos	Others
ETK		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RDIUP		0	0	3	0	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UKH		0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NIRO		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AUSL-RE		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UoM		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
McM		0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CIJ		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NISON		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHZ		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SWP S		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
INT		0	0	7	1	8	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UdE		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HWRU		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 25: Monitoring tool - Global monitoring sheet

Figure 26: Monitoring tool – Dashboard

	Linkedin	Youtube	Tiktok	Facebook	Twitter
Followers	115	13	423	38	10

Figure 27: Monitoring tool – Followers

Audiences	Details	Reached Number
Young people	School pupils, university students, young patients, young migrants	300
Group1 (10-14)	First group	0
Group2 (15-18)	Second group	0
Group3 (19-24)	Third group	0
Teachers	Educators	0
Parents	Parents of adolescents	0
Schools	where adolescents are studying	0
Academia	universities, schools, young researchers, scientists and RTOs	624
Healthcare professionals	clinicians, hospitals and clinics, Psychologists,	0
Businesses	SMEs, Start-ups, Med industries, services providers	0
Policymakers and regulators	Authorities, governments, public supervisors, agencies, industries, EC Representatives.	0
Investors	banks, business angels, health-insurances,	0
Others	NGO, society at large	0

Figure 28: Monitoring tool – Audience reached

Monitoring tool guidelines

The following text is shown together with the monitoring tool above, to agree on the content of the tool and explain how to fill it in.

- Any video creation will be in social media “type of activities”.
- In case of specific activities addressed target group, we split young people into 3 groups.
- Include all content published on corporate/organizational accounts and briefly describe the activity,
- Include event name, dates and place, title of the presentation.
- Include any dissemination activity (for example also awareness activities in b2b meetings, material preparation, etc.).
- Scientific publications refer to any peer-reviewed articles in specialized journals and other publications.

4.3. Expected impact of the dissemination and communication activities

Thanks to the monitoring tool presented above, the consortium will be well-equipped to thoroughly assess the impact of the various dissemination and communication actions.

The data collected will be analysed against our pre-set KPI’s, enabling us to draw conclusive insights into the overall impact and success of our dissemination process.

Table 10: Project D&C Key Performance Indicators

Dissemination output	Output measurements
Final Event	At least 100 participants and a high satisfaction index
Website	At least 25000 unique website visitors
Newsletters	At least 150 newsletters subscribers
Press and News releases	Hundreds of online readers reached
Videos	250 views per video in 12 months from release
Twitter	At least 250 Twitter followers At least 500 retweets and/or likes per year
Facebook	Over 250 likes on Facebook per year
LinkedIn	Over 250 LinkedIn members
TikTok	2000 views on TikTok / year
Public deliverables	5000 visits and 100 downloads per public deliverable one year after the project’s end

Workshops	20 participants (organisations) each
Joint actions	Involve at least 20 multidisciplinary members in the SMILE community

Partners tasks and responsibilities

The table below outlines the duration and primary leadership for the sub-tasks within WP8.

The allocation of tasks and leadership roles, as depicted in this table, is vital to have clear guidance on the timeframes and key personnel responsible for each sub-task. These details are intended to facilitate smooth collaboration, accountability, and the efficient achievement of WP8's objectives.

Table 11: Partners' tasks and responsibilities

Tasks and Responsibilities Distribution WP8. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation			
Overall Leadership	RDIUP		
Tasks	Leader	Participating	Months
T8.1.	RDIUP	ALL	M1-M42
T8.2	CIP	ALL	M6-M42
T8.3	RDIUP	ALL	M9-M42
T8.4	FTK	ALL	M3-M42

Partner communication contacts

Partners have designated from their respective organizations one person to oversee communication activities at the partner level. The person in charge will be responsible for following the guidelines outlined in this document.

To ensure smooth interaction and communication management among partners, the table below provides the name and contact information of these persons:

Table 12: Communication representatives

Partner	Person in charge of communication	Email Address
FTK	Jana Mertens	jmertens@ftk.de
RDIUP	Habib Nasser	Habib.nasser@rdiup.com
Universitätsklinikum Heidelberg	Gwen Mayer	gwendolyn.mayer@med.uni-heidelberg.de
Nurogames Gmbh	Yash Shekhawat	yash.shekhawat@nuromedia.com

Project Number: 101080923

Project Acronym: SMILE

Heriot-Watt University	Mel Mckendrick	M.McKendrick@hw.ac.uk
Azienda Unita Sanitaria Locale-Irccs Di Reggio Emilia	Vincenza Frisardi	vincenza.frisardi@aosp.bo.it>
Univerza V Mariboru	Urška Smrke	urska.smrke@um.si
Mestna Obcina Maribor	Jasmina Dolinsek	jasmina.dolinsek@maribor.si
CIP Citizens In Power	Natasa Andronikou	natasa.a@citizensinpower.org
N Vision Systems and Technologies SL	Zouhair Haddi	zouhair.haddi@nvision.es
Wiz Development & Services SRL	Diana Butean	diana@butean.com
Swps Uniwersytet Humanistycznospoleczny	Ewelina Smoktunowicz	esmoktunowicz@swps.edu.pl
Fundacion Intras	Rosa Almeida	rra@intras.es
The University of Edinburgh	Matthias Schwannauer	m.schwannauer@ed.ac.uk hos.health@ed.ac.uk

5. Introduction to the exploitation plan

SMILE's exploitation plan will be structured in seven steps. This strategy, when put into action, will ensure a smooth transition of the project's outcomes into the market upon the project's conclusion. The ultimate objective of the exploitation plan is not only to harness the project's results but also to generate fresh business opportunities. The exploitation methodology will be structured around the following key steps:

- The identification of the innovative KERs: The first step involves pinpointing the most innovative and valuable outcomes of the project, which hold the potential for further development and commercialization.
- The documentation of an analytical IPR management strategy: In this phase, we will create a robust strategy for managing intellectual property rights associated with our key exploitable results.
- The conduction of a thorough market analysis: A market analysis will be conducted to gain insights into market trends, needs, and potential niches for our solutions.
- The definition of exploitation models: We will analytically define all potential commercial and non-commercial exploitation models, considering diverse scenarios.
- The evaluation of business model viability: An in-depth analysis will be performed to assess the sustainability and viability of the various business models under consideration.
- The validation of value propositions: We will validate the value propositions of our KERs and assess the assumptions underpinning our business models.
- The development of go-to-market strategy: The final step will involve crafting a comprehensive go-to-market, branding, and overall exploitation strategy to ensure the successful introduction of our innovations into the market.

Figure 29: Steps to Exploitation plan

This stepwise approach is planned to maximize the impact of SMILE project's results, create tangible benefits for the target audience, and foster innovation in the field of mental health support.

Exploitation objectives and roadmap

SMILE's exploitation strategy will follow 2 main phases of expansion with specific short-term, and long-term objectives:

Years 1-4 (2023-2026) - SMILE Project Implementation

This phase encompasses several key objectives:

- **Technology advancement:** the goal is to advance the SMILE platform to Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL7). It involves refining the platform's features, capabilities, and user-friendliness to ensure its effectiveness in addressing mental health challenges in young individuals.
- **Intellectual Property Protection:** The goal is to put in place a robust strategy to safeguard the IPR associated with the exploitable outcomes of the project to ensure that the innovations remain secure.
- **Policy and Strategy Development:** Strategic policy frameworks will be devised to guide the integration of SMILE's solutions into the broader mental health landscape. This entails aligning with relevant policies and regulations to ensure ethical and responsible deployment.
- **Awareness and Community build-up activities:** The goal is to lay the foundation for a robust SMILE membership community. The consortium will hold awareness campaigns and community engagement activities to achieve the target SMILE membership community, at least 500 potential users from targeted stakeholder groups.

Years 5-8 (2026-2030) - Commercialization and Expansion

This phase marks a critical transition in the SMILE project's journey. SMILE tools will be developed to TRL9 and commercialized. The primary objectives of this phase include:

- Commercialization: A dedicated start-up, 'SMILE DIAG,' will spearhead the commercialization efforts, with a targeted market launch by 2027-2028.
- Community Growth: The goal for 2030 is to establish a 1000-strong SMILE membership community to contribute to driving approximately 5% of the global adolescent mental health screening and diagnosis market.
- Continued Research and Development: Even in the commercialization phase, R&D activities will remain a key focus. These activities ensure that the SMILE tools remain cutting-edge, effective, and responsive to evolving mental health needs.
- Dissemination and Marketing: To achieve widespread adoption, dissemination and marketing activities will continue, with a strategic allocation of 10% and 20% of revenue generated for marketing and R&D, respectively.

5.1. Key Expected Results

The KERs serve as the foundation upon which we are building a dynamic strategy for further development and commercialization. Below, we outline the 9 KERs, the partners involved in their realization, and the strategic pathways to leverage their full potential. Together, these KERs encompass the essence of our commitment to advancing mental health support for young individuals, both technologically and strategically.

Table 13: The 9 KERs, the partners involved and the ES.

Nr	KER	Partners	Exploitation strategy
KER1	SMILE gamification platform	UoM, NURO, HWU	Licensing and sponsorship
KER2	Self-Assessment and Monitoring Framework (SAMF)	UoM, MoM, UKH, HWU	Consultancy services, publication and technological transfer
KER3	KM-EP	FTK, RDIUP	One-stop-shop of tools, SMILE DIAG spin off and commercialization of solutions and services SaaS, e-learning services
KER4	Awareness Mobile APP	RDIUP, UKH, HWU	Make the app available to apps-stores, sponsorship, peer support services, rewarding business, ADS
KER5	SMILE OKP	UKH, UoM, HWU, RDIUP, NION, FTK	Open access KB
KER6	Explainable DSSs and GUIs	NION, RDIUP, UoM, UKH, HWU	Consultancy services (e.g., nutritional, fitness recommendations), research, expert support services
KER7	Exploitation, branding and business strategies	All partners	SMILE-DIAG spinoff, commercialization of DLT-based and AI-driven (out/inpatient) services, DLT-based rewarding business

KER8	Competences building tutorials, MOOC	MoM, FTK, all pilots	Massive open online course, training e-learning services, excellence centres
KER9	Common semantically interoperable data models	UoM, MoM, HWU, WIZ, RDIUP	Decision/policy making services, knowledge selling

Besides these 9 KERs, we have 5 other expected results:

- 7 pilots in different countries
- An evidence-based knowledge base, DLT-based rewarding system, interactive chatbot, and nutritional & fitness protocols within KM-EP
- At least 3 scientific publications with Gold Open Access
- At least 4 dedicated workshops with potential end-users and experts
- Ethical framework and policy recommendations

5.2. Preliminary market analysis

According to Precedence Research, the global digital health market (big data, cloud computing, IoT, gamification) was valued at USD 270.60 billion in 2021 and is expected to reach over USD 1354.68 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR 19.2% during the forecast period 2022 to 2030.

The market is segmented by 3 main components: hardware, software and services, with services accounting for approximately 65% of the total market share. This impressive growth can be attributed to the increasing demand for mobile health APPs and the expanding adoption of digital health solutions in emerging economies worldwide.

In our initial competitor analysis, we have identified a noteworthy gap in the market. Currently, there is no open platform that offers personalized and holistic SMILE services (Figure 30) and value proposition. Which positions SMILE favourably in the market landscape.

Figure 30: Holistic SMILE services

SWOT analysis

The analysis of the overall strategic position of the SMILE ecosystem/business is provided in a SWOT analysis (table below). The SWOT analysis aims to identify strategic avenues that can facilitate the development of a unique business model tailored to SMILE's core competencies and the dynamic demands of its operating environment. By conducting this SWOT analysis, we aim to leverage SMILE's strengths to maximize opportunities in the market, mitigate weaknesses and convert them into strengths where possible, and identify and prepare for potential threats that may impact the SMILE ecosystem or joint venture company.

Table 14: SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The consortium's strong multidisciplinary expertise - Strategic and useful case studies in 7 EU countries - Using Open technologies and services (HW/SW) - Strong background in building synergies and solver communities. - SMILE partners hold IPs and patents - Engagement of multi-stakeholders - SMILE partners adopted guidelines for data protection - Strong commercialization and go-to-market capabilities (5 multidisciplinary SMEs involved) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of sponsors and low visibility at the beginning, SMILE will carry out active efforts through communication to raise awareness. - High front-up costs of investment to develop and implement innovative technologies. SMILE is looking for EU funds to finance development and go-to-market activities. - Digital services are not known in the market enough. <p>This issue will be addressed by the development and promotion of the brand via marketing and other communication channels.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Needs of digital solutions in healthcare sector - Raising demand for open solutions and services to contribute to overcoming the post Covid crisis. - Rising demand for gamified methods in education - Increase need of cost-effective ways for home/school - Many programs and fundings encourage disruptive technologies and business models in healthcare - Emerging standards for semantic interoperability across domains - Increasing awareness of the benefits of AI-based modules and more interest in digital and smart tools - Early-entrant advantage and low competition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient resources to provide low-cost services and full open solutions - Complex regulations and policies constraints - Lack of qualified personnel - Human acceptability and reluctance for disruptive methods, - Healthcare disparities and inequities - Difficulties accessing and using data of patients. - Economic crisis caused by Covid-19 and Ukrainian war <p>These threats can be mitigated by engaging regulatory bodies, policy makers and communities. Data security will be ensured by DLT.</p>

Preliminary business plan and financial projections

To ensure the continuity and the autonomy of SMILE post-project, the SMILE tools will generate revenues based on the following profitable activities:

- **Pay Per Click (PPC):** This revenue source, exemplified by Google AdSense, involves advertisers paying a fee each time one of their ads is clicked.
- **Sponsorship:** SMILE aims to provide users with rewards for completing certain in-app actions, such as audience reach, duration, or evaluations. SMILE earns revenue by taking a share of the earnings from redeemed rewards.
- **SMILE services:** Additional services offered by SMILE including e-training courses, decision assistance, recommender system (e.g., fitness and nutritional), complex association and behaviour analysis, and pedagogical advisory will be paid by health organizations and companies.
- **Marketing sensitive knowledge and data:** SMILE will offer open access to best practices, a knowledge base, statistics and free training courses. However, meaningful data (Gaia-X model) can be sold to health companies and research institutions while complying with security and ethical aspects.

Assuming a humble estimation of about 20 companies and private entities using our tools by the end of the first-year post-launch, (due to our potential, the interest of external stakeholders and replication cases) with an expected annual increase of 25% over 4 years, mainly from SMILE cloud-based services.

In addition to the monetized benefits, SMILE will deliver non-monetized profits and outcomes such as sharing knowledge and increasing awareness about climate change, as well as contributing to the comfort and well-being of citizens.

5.3. Sustainable Business plan

Our strategy is expected to facilitate the transition of simple healthcare procedures and services from hospitals to homes. Such business strategies supporting diagnosis measures and self-monitoring of health may render healthcare more affordable, as they deliver care at lower costs and offer alternatives to hospital and physician practices. Our business model will focus mainly on the sale of AI-driven services and expertise. In the long term, SMILE (e.g., SaaS) is potentially targeting high level service provision for government, policy makers, educational institutions and healthcare providers. However, the immediate target markets are the low-level services for adolescents, teachers, clinicians and parents (e.g., inpatient and outpatient services).

Initial SMILE business model canvas

The economic sustainability of SMILE is presented in the table 15. and was established by the Business Model Canvas parameters: financial performance, key partners, activities, resources, value proposition to customers, customer relationship and distribution channels, customer segments, the cost structure, and the revenue streams. Further analysis of individual services will be developed during the project.

Table 15: Initial SMILE Business Model Canvas

Key partners UNIVs SMILE consortium European commission Open Technologies providers Regulatory agencies Investors Influencers GOVs & policy makers Communities	Key activities Co-design AI tools Research and innovation Data protection and privacy Define tailored business models Engage & Train Establish PPPs Key resources Pool of experts Infrastructures, IPRs Open platform Solver community	Key propositions Tackle barriers & risks Reduce assessment costs & times Increase awareness and resilience Enable online digital access of knowledge Resilience building Gamified monitoring and pedagogies Supporting European SMEs and startups Identifying technological and market gaps Fair sharing of benefits Data-driven services Enabling quality and security by design	Customer relationship User-friendly solutions Cost-effectiveness Open innovation & open access Digital Single Market Public deliverables Equity Branding Channels Platform, website, forums, tutorials Distributors, stores GitHub Media Open source	Customer segments B2B SMEs Industries Health companies Business to public (B2P) Hospitals GOVs Municipalities Institutions B2C Adolescents Parents
Cost infrastructure Events organizations Fixed costs Networking Branding & Marketing Personnel costs Cloud, Equipment Staff training		Revenues streams Memberships & sponsoring ADs Licensing Rewards Commissions Donations Funding Cloud services		

SMILE Branding Strategy

In the realm of SMILE, our brand is more than just a logo or marketing material, it's a reflection of our collective vision and values. In the table 16. below, we present the SMILE branding strategy, that encompasses the fundamental aspects of our brand, including the SMILE vision, purpose, values, and guidelines for brand integration.

The SMILE branding strategy will not only shape our brand's identity, but also help us leave a lasting impact on our target audience and stakeholders.

Table 16: The initial Branding strategy

SMILE Vision	SMILE Purpose
- Open and collaborative platform for adolescent resilience building and self-monitoring, - Enabling clinicians, teachers, SMEs and researchers to seamlessly set up novel methods and pedagogies, - Providing healthcare value chain open tools to improve responsiveness to psychological distress.	- Help EU healthcare diagnosis sectors to adopt open innovation platform that will lead to quality by design, reducing costs, and expediting the adoption of high-value clinical practices. - Unroll a wide range of entirely new business opportunities with SMEs contributing to the betterment of society. - Develop and commercialize open solutions equipping the EU healthcare value chain with digital tools to rapidly diagnose and support mental health assessment while reducing time and cost.
SMILE Values	Brand Integration and guidelines

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamified assessment/monitoring self- • Openness and affordability • Co-creative R&D and innovation, • High quality practices, and • End-user satisfaction and acceptance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brand story, positioning statements and attractive pitch deck - Build consistent brand to reinforce SMILE image including logo, marketing materials and visual identity (e.g., videos) - Reflect SMILE’s aims and vision in the recruitment and training of staff - Develop SMILE platform support and customer relations to implement our vision - Reinforce awareness of SMILE brand via promotional and marketing materials including digital campaigns
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5.4. Individual exploitation actions by the consortium

SMILE will develop an overall exploitation roadmap to attract national and international stakeholders. The roadmap will categorize exploitation opportunities in short-term, medium-term and long-term prospects. Here is how each partner plans to leverage the project results:

FTK:

- Creating new assets and improving know-how in access control, medical data management (KER9), semantic portals, and DLT(KER7).
- Exploiting results in academic publications and new projects.
- Distributing results through SMILE DIAG and conducting sales of access control and knowledge management tools and services via KM-EP(KER3).

RDIUP:

- Acquiring new experiences and know-how related to mental health diagnosis and assessment, especially in nutritional and fitness recommendations (from KER6 and KER8).
- Expanding their network in the healthcare sector in Europe.
- Aiming to commercialize their Mobile awareness APP (KER4) through SMILE DIAG (KER7) and replicate the reward system in other sectors.

NURO:

- Eager to present the project and exploit software modules to acquire new clients and projects.
- Exploring new opportunities to expand into the digital health market.
- Leveraging SMILE gamification (KER1 and KER2) platform as a benchmark for new market areas.

HWU:

- Utilizing SMILE OKP (KER5) and gamified platform (KER1 and KER2) to identify unmet clinical needs in mental health.
- Strengthening research capabilities and ability to tailor appropriate help for adolescents with psychological distress. Data will be integrated and combined (KER9) with MIND Lab data within the Global Research Institute of Health and Care Engineering to provide new curated datasets.
- Intending to engage stakeholders outside of SMILE for adoption of the SMILE ecosystem (KER7).

UoM:

- Integrating knowledge (KER 3 to KER 5) from SMILE related to Explainable AI (KER6), observable biomarkers, and gamification in data collection and intervention in ongoing multidisciplinary research on real-world data collection, risk assessment, and personalized preventive care.
- Incorporating SMILE results into pre-PhD courses and involves at least 10 students through student projects, master and PhD theses addressing elements of SMILE.
- Planning to lead a COST Action built around SMILE.

MoM:

- Reaching out to schools and NGOs for helping young people through seminars, workshops, and debates.
- Exploiting SMILE to better understand the origins and risks in the local environment and create citizen-centric social policies.
- Designing new citizen support policies, led by local and regional NGOs, for building resilience capacity and developing coping strategies.

NION:

- Acquiring new skills in the precision medicine sector.
- Exploiting the DSS (KER6) and OKP (KER3) results to extend commercial offers and reach new clients.
- Offering IPs generated by NION to SMILE DIAG through license or technology transfer.

WIZ:

- Improving the experience in building citizen-centric applications and data operations.
- Improve its experience in data operations (KER9) to guarantee data provenance and certify the output analytics.

Pilots: INT, UoE, UKH, MoM, CIP, SWPS, IRCCS:

- Capitalizing on SMILE's experience in AI (KER6) and gamification (KER1-2) for health (prevention, diagnosis, therapeutics) and wellbeing.
- Transforming all pilots into excellence centres
- Exploiting results for the design of new citizen support policies and inclusion in educational and social awareness programs (INTRAS leads one as a care provider Exploitation workshops).

Joint exploitation of the results

The joint exploitation strategy and the business plan will be defined at M12, reviewed at M24 and delivered at M42. This consortium will define 2 joint exploitations of the expected findings, knowledge, learning, technologies and services.

The creation of a training organization

The purpose of this spinoff is to train actors working on issues around adolescent psychological distress to take charge of configuration and use of our digital modules. The concept aims at valorising the SMILE Tools such as KM-EP, through training sessions (bioinformatics, psychology, gamification and biomarkers fields), and providing user support dedicated to education and healthcare providers and facilitators. The certified training scheme and revenues will be defined by RDIUP.

The creation of a new start-up

The SMILE DIAG start-up have 4 main activities:

- **Sales of Digital Tools:** Primarily, the gamification framework, Decision Support Systems (DSSs), Knowledge Management for Evidence-Based Practices (KM-EP), and applications (APPs).
- **Platform Maintenance and Health Services:** Ensuring the continuous operation of the platform and providing accessible health-related services.
- **Community and Market Expansion:** Organizing networking events and engaging with members to grow the community and market presence.
- **Policy Advocacy:** Influencing policymakers by advocating for reduced regulatory constraints and policy implementation through lobbying actions.

The infrastructure, the revenues, memberships and costs of the SMILE DIAG will be defined by RDIUP.

Partner's responsibilities and roles in SMILE

Before delving into the specifics of the partner's roles within the exploitation phase, the table 17. below provides an overview to understand the partner's key contributions and responsibilities within the project.

Table 17: Partners' main roles in SMILE

Partner	Main roles in SMILE
FTK	General Project Coordination, development of KM-EP, Authorization Infrastructure
RDIUP	RDIUP leads WP8 and develop the data analytics, rewarding system and mobile APP
NURO	Gamification concepts, implementation of serious games
HWU	Contribute to the gamification development and lead the WP3
UoM	Development of the SAMF and interactive chatbot
NION	Leading WP5, development of the DSS module and deployment of the OKP
WIZ	Leading WP6 and development of middleware and data harmonization and integration
Pilots: INT, UoE, SWPS, MoM, IRCCS,	Stakeholder engagement and requirements elicitation through a co-creation and agile process. Case studies and Scenarios requirements, help in the co-design of the SMILE Framework and interventions, study design and

UKH, CIP	coordinating Living Lab testing and pilot, working on business cases with the regional and national specificities and policies, communication and dissemination.
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Partner’s industrial and commercialization roles

During the exploitation phase, each partner plays a crucial role in driving SMILE's industrial and commercialization objectives. This section outlines the responsibilities of each partner in leveraging and advancing the project's results.

Table 18: Partners’ industrial and commercial roles in SMILE

Partners	Industrial and commercialization of SMILE results
FTK	Spin-off exploiting the authorization tools improved and developed. Also license the improved KM-EP to knowledge intensive industries, such as medical, data science, education, and engineering.
RDIUP	Post project, RDIUP will lead SMILE DIAG, and a reasonable and fair royalty and compensation will be required (pay-as-you-use). Also, RDIUP will replicate solutions in other sectors and reach new market
NION	NION will provide royalty-free access for our digital tools (OKP, XAI-based DSS and frontends) during the development of the project.
NURO	NURO will commercialize, license and lead the replication of the gamification framework and engine and provide a license for SMILE DIAG.
WIZ	WIZ will identify new market opportunities for the data modules and reach out investors and founders
CIP	CIP will create a training centre in the fields of global education, social innovation, entrepreneurship, well-being and sustainable growth
Universities	Identify new market exploitation through technological transfer into local industries and contribute to the SMILE DIAG through training courses.
All pilots	They will be transformed into excellence centres and innovation hubs to co-create spin-offs and support local startups developing their products.
INTRAS	Support scaling-up/ commercialization of products in the health field (owned or part of a client portfolio).

5.5. Intellectual Property Management Strategy

In line with H2020 participation regulations, our consortium will be guided by the CA signed by all partners. This agreement specifies ownership, the nature of knowledge, potential for exploitation, access rights, and measures for protecting IP. Additionally, we will establish exploitation agreements between results co-owners of project results and other SMILE partners to further outline exploitation and IPR based on the CA.

Given the numerous potential exploitable results and new business model possibilities, we will adopt advanced IP strategies to maximize the value of our innovations. These strategies include:

- **Securing Main Exploitable Results:** Our primary approach is to secure IPR including patenting whenever possible to empower partners to fully exploit their strengths and innovations.
- **Overall IP Strategy:** This encompasses the evaluation of knowledge generated within the project. It involves defining the scope of IP, assessing patentability, exploring protection options, and evaluating the commercialization potential of these assets.
- **Legal Requirements for Commercialization:** This task involves conducting a 'freedom to operate' analysis to ensure that our innovations do not infringe upon existing patents or IP. It also includes developing patent filing strategies, submitting patent applications for promising results, and drafting of commercial agreements such as joint ventures, manufacturing partnerships, distribution and licensing agreements, to ensure the effective and responsible exploitation of our IP assets.
- **Identification of Competitive Risks:** To ensure that we are well-prepared in a competitive landscape, we will systematically map our IP to identify potential competitors and address competitive risks effectively.

In support of these IP and exploitation activities, we have planned two internal IP exploitation workshops. These workshops will provide valuable guidance and expertise to our consortium partners.

Data Protection and Intellectual Property Management

The project consortium will establish a Data Management Plan (DMP) to handle project-generated data, both non-confidential and exploitable information. The DMP will outline the principles and processes for data collection, organization, management, storage, security, analysis and sharing throughout the project's duration. The primary purpose of the DMP is to ensure the safeguarding of data integrity and confidentiality where applicable.

The joint actions also include planning actions and activities aimed at establishing links with local communities, stakeholders and policymakers. The SMILE consortium aims to develop a stakeholder network through its communication and dissemination activities such as events and conference participation and organization. For this reason, the Registration of Interest form is currently under development, and its primary focus is to collect essential contact details. Additionally, we are considering optional fields, including participant profiles, country, city, and areas of potential interest in the project, all of which will help tailor participants' involvement. A fundamental requirement for this form is securing GDPR consent, which enables contact sharing within the consortium and for project-related purposes. To support this endeavour, a Stakeholder Identification Dataset has been created by CIP, inviting all consortium members to register local, national, European and International stakeholders alongside their prospective interest, involvement and impact in SMILE activities. This will allow the development of the SMILE stakeholder network, inviting their contribution in various activities at both national and international level.

A first draft will be created and updated periodically during the project.

Personal Photographs of people

Utilization of personal photos or videos on social media or other publicly accessible platforms requires the consent of individuals who are identifiable. All SMILE members have confirmed their consent to use their personal photos and pictures in our website, social media and public deliverables. On the other hand, for individuals external to the consortium who will be involved in the research, permission to use their likeness will be sought and obtained prior to any form of publication.

6. Conclusions

This document presents the dissemination and communication plan that will be followed during the lifespan of the project describing all the materials and strategies that will be used for external communication, engagement and uptake of the results by relevant stakeholders. This document helps to increase the impact of the work the project is delivering and should help us all in contributing to a successful project,

This comprises the project's existing and upcoming dissemination resources, the events, workshops, and conferences that are of particular interest to the project from a dissemination/exploitation perspective, as well as the communities targeted by the project for dissemination and engagement efforts.

It is anticipated that more dissemination and exploitation opportunities will arise as the project progresses. Therefore, the consortium will use this plan as an initial strategy subject to updates and reviews.

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